

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF CFRP USING CNF (Carbon Nano-Fiber) DISPERSED RESIN

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SUMMARY: Static strength tests were carried out for CFRP laminates using carbon nanofiber (CNF) dispersed resin. The CNF dispersed resin was impregnated to CF reinforcement and cured by hot press. Used CNF was cup-stacked type of nanofiber, CARBERE[®], made by GSI CREOS Corporation. Two types of CNF aspect ratios were employed. These fiber length of the CNF were controlled about 1 μ m (AR10) and 5 μ m (AR50), respectively. The CNF was dispersed to EPIKOTE 827[®] epoxy resin. CNF weight proportions were 5% and 10% of the resin. Curing agent employed was aromatic amine EPIKURE W[®]. TORAYCA[®] C6343 (T300 3K 198 g/m²) plain woven fabric was used for reinforcement of the CFRP laminates. Cure condition was 100 °C for two hours and 175 °C for four hours. As the static strength test results, CFRP laminates with the CNF dispersed resin show higher compressive strength than CFRP laminates without CNF as control. It is concluded that impregnation of the CNF dispersed resin to the CF reinforcement may improve CFRP laminates strength in compressive loading. There is a tendency that weight proportion of the CNF may affect compression strength of the CFRP laminates so far the present test results.

KEYWORDS: nano composite, carbon nanofiber, cup-stacked type, CFRP laminates, compression strength

INTRODUCTION

It is well known that carbon nanotube (CNT) or nanofiber (CNF) exhibits extremely high elastic modulus and strengths. One trend in CNT application as composites reinforcement is direct dispersion like chopped fiber in polymer with an alignment as parallel as possible, which is considered as two-phase material of CNT and polymer. As two-phase material of CNT reinforced composites, Xu *et al.* [1] determined elastic modulus of multi-walled carbon nanofiber (MWNT) reinforced epoxy composite thin films. Dispersing very low volume fraction of the MWNT to epoxy, only 0.1wt%, resulted in 20% increase in elastic modulus of composite thin films. Qian and Dickey *et al.* [2] also reported that 1wt% MWNT composite films were 36%-42% and up to 25% increase in elastic modulus and break stress. One of the applications of CNT reinforced polymer for filament wound CFRP was demonstrated by Spindler-Ranta and Bakis [3]. They measured SWNT added epoxy composite of 1wt% for tensile modulus and strength. Moreover, they measured compressive modulus and strength for filament wound CFRP rings using 1-wt% SWNT in polymer matrix. However, this study was concluded that SWNT did not give noticeable affect in the CNT reinforced composites and filament wound CFRP rings. On the other hand, Iwahori and Ishikawa [4] reported that compressive strength were improved by CFRP laminates using cup-stacked type carbon nanofiber (CSNF)

dispersed epoxy as three-phase material.

In this paper, two different length of CSNF dispersed epoxy were employed. Moreover, each CSNF was dispersed to epoxy resin with the ratio of 5-wt% and 10-wt%. Using these resins, CSNF reinforced composites and CFRP laminates were fabricated. The mechanical properties of the CSNF reinforced composites were tested in tension, compression and flexure. The CFRP using CSNF dispersed resins were also tested in tension and compression. Figure 1 shows a concept of CNF added resin as matrix of CF reinforced plastics. The goal of this concept is improvement in weak points of mechanical properties of CFRP laminates such as compression strengths or interlaminar strengths. It is prospected that compressive strength may be improved as the CNF is functioning as matrix modifier, and that interlaminar strength may also be improved by CNF bridging in the polymer matrix as crack propagation resistance.

Fig. 1 The concept of mechanical properties improvement for CFRP laminates

CARBON NANOFIBER

Cup-stacked type nanofiber (CSNF):

Figure 2 shows the schematic view of CARBERE[®] manufactured by GSI CREOS Corporation. This type of CNF is called “cup-stacked type carbon nanofiber” (CSNF). This CSNF has novel structural characteristics such as large hollow core and their large portion of open edges. Several layers of truncated conical graphene sheets are stacking and placing each other like metal bellows. The basic type of carbon nanotubes, multi-walled nanotubes (MWNTs) and single-walled nanotubes (SWNTs), have 0.6-50nm in diameter [3][6] typically. The diameter range of CSNFs is

Fig. 2 Schematic view of cup-stacked type carbon nanofiber

80 to 100 nm and their length is up to 200 micrometer. The CSNF growth conditions can be precisely controlled in production by CVD. The CSNF shows long and straight appearance and the large hollow cores as demonstrated in Figure 3. Stacking morphology of truncated conical sheets exhibits some angles to the fiber axis, a large portion of the graphene edges are exposed to the outside. This configuration of CSNF suggests the advantage in load transfer between CSNF and polymer matrix. Figures 4(a) (b) are TEM images of CSNFs that are called AR10 (a) and AR50 (b), respectively. The length of AR10 is approximately 500 nm-1.0 micrometer and AR50 is 2.5-10.0 micrometer.

Fig. 3 TEM image of CSNF and magnified image for CSNF wall

Fig. 4 TEM image of different length of CSNFs
(a) AR10 (b) AR50

Mechanical properties of normal CNTs are over 1TPa in elastic modulus and as high as 600GPa in strength [3][6]. Figure 5 shows mechanical properties of the CSNF superimposed on properties of carbon fibers (CFs). The strength of CSNF is much lower than normal CNTs properties. However, the CSNF shows still higher mechanical properties than CFs.

Fig. 5 Comparison of CSNF and carbon fibers in mechanical properties

PREPARATION OF TEST SPECIMENS

Before discussing mechanical properties, explanations about material preparations must be given. Two kinds in length of CSNFs, AR10 and AR50, are employed. An epoxy resin EP827[®] (Japan Epoxy Resin Co. Ltd.) and a hardener of aromatic amine EPIKURE W[®] (Japan Epoxy Resin Co. Ltd.) are also employed. Before the hardener was added, AR10-35wt% and AR50-25wt% dispersed resins (compounds) were diluted with pure epoxy resin to 5-wt% and 10-wt% respectively. Dilution of the compounds were mixed mechanically in 80°C for 30 minutes. Subsequently to the dilution process, the hardener was added and mixed for another 15 minutes. The CSNF dispersed resins, 5-wt% and 10-wt%, were hold on 80°C for another 30 minutes in vacuumed chamber. The curing process of CSNF composites, i.e. cured CSNF dispersed resins without CF fabric, was 100 °C for 75 minutes and 175 °C for 4 hours by hot press.

The reinforcement of CFRP laminates with CSNF is TORAYCA[®] CO6343 (T300 3K plain woven fabric; ±0/90) 20plys. The CSNF dispersed resins were prepared identically as much as possible with CSNF composites and impregnated into cut and laid dry preform at 80 °C and vacuumed again. The same cure process was introduced to the CFRP. Four types of specimens were prepared: neat EP827 resin as control and CFRP without CSNF as control, CSNF composites and CFRP using CSNF dispersed resin. After the curing, test specimens were cut by a diamond blade cutting machine. Table 1 shows the type of CSNF, weight fraction of CSNF, volume fraction of CSNF, sizes and number of test specimens for CSNF composites. Table 2 also shows the condition of specimens for CFRP laminates. Those wt% of CSNF are weight fraction to EP827 neat resin, and Vf% of CSNF are volume fraction to reinforced composites or CFRP laminates.

Table 1. Specimen conditions for CSNF composites

	Type of CSNF	CSNF wt%	Vf% of CSNF	Test	Size of specimens	Number of specimens
CSNF composites	AR10 AR50	0	0	Tension	10.0x110x4	N=3 (Each)
		5	2.1			
		10	4.1			
		0	0	Compression	10.0x52x4	
		5	2.1			
		10	4.1			
		0	0	Flexure	10.0x110x4	
		5	2.1			
		10	4.1			

Table 2. Specimen conditions for CFRP laminates using CSNF dispersed resins.

	Type of CSNF	CSNF wt%	Vf % of CSNF	Vf% of CF (20plys=4.0 mm)	Test	Size of specimens	Number of specimens
CFRP	AR10 AR50	0	0	56	Tension	10.0*110*4.0	N=3 (Each)
		5	0.9				
		10	1.8				
		0	0		Compression	10.0*52*4.0	
		5	0.9				
		10	1.8				

TEST RESULTS

1. Mechanical properties of CSNF reinforced composites

Tension: Static tensile strengths and modulus of CSNF composites were tested in an Instron 8502 hydraulic testing machine. The crosshead speed was chosen as 1.0 mm/min and an extensometer was used for strain measurements. A picture of a tensile test is shown in Figure 6. Figure 7 shows stress-strain curves for EP827 neat resin, and composites with AR50-5wt% and AR50-10wt%. Table 3 shows the averaged test results of tensile strength and modulus of three data for all types of materials without CF fabric. It was found that all CSNF reinforced composites improved more or less in tensile modulus and strength. A remarkable improvement for elastic modulus and strength were observed for CSNF-wt10% composites. AR50-10wt% composite exhibits 45% and 22% higher than tensile modulus and strength of neat resin, although maximum strain was the lowest value among all materials.

Fig. 6 Picture of Tensile test

Fig. 7 Strain-Stress curves in tension for CSNF composites (AR50)

Table 3. Results of tensile test for CSNF composites

Resin	Weight% of CSNF and specimens	Tensile Modulus* (GPa)	Effects to modulus(%)	Max. Stress (MPa)	Effects to Max. Stress(%)	Max. Strain (μ st)	Effects to strain(%)
EP827	No CSNF	2.479	-	72.9	-	63193	-
CNF composites	AR10-5%	2.826	+14.0	77.7	+6.60	52490	-16.9
	AR10-10%	3.628	+46.3	85.4	+17.2	38796	-38.6
	AR50-5%	2.636	+6.40	75.1	+3.00	48534	-23.2
	AR50-10%	3.602	+45.3	88.6	+21.6	37507	-40.7

*Elastic modulus was determined by slope of stress-strain curve between 500 μ strain and 2500 μ strain.

Compression: Static compressive modulus of CSNF composites were measured a screw driven Instron 4482 testing machine. For elastic modulus measurements, the test specimens were compressed by both platens as shown in Figure 8. Static compressive strength tests of CSNF composites were conducted with an Instron 8502 hydraulic testing machine. The speed of crosshead was chosen as 0.5 mm/min. These specimens were directly clamped by hydraulic grips of the testing machine with the inter-grip distance of 14.0 mm. Figure 9 shows stress-displacement curves for EP827 neat resin, and composites with AR50-5wt% and AR50-10wt%. Yield-like behavior was observed and “yield” stress was assumed that the first stress point where displacement increasing rate was saturated or changed from decrease to increase. Table 4 shows the averaged test results of compressive yield stress and modulus of three data for all types of specimens without CF fabric. From these results, AR10-10wt% and AR50-5wt% composites were slightly higher in yield stress and modulus than neat EP827 resin as control. A noticeable result was AR50-10Wt% composite properties such that with yield stress and modulus are improved in 46% and 16%, respectively.

Fig. 8 Picture of compressive modulus test

Fig. 9 Strain–displacement curves in compression for CSNF composites (AR50)

Table 4. Results of compressive test for CSNF composites

Resin	Weight of CNF	Compression modulus(GPa)	Effects to modulus* (%)	Yield. Stress (MPa)	Effects to yield stress(%)
EP827	No CSNF	-2.756	-	-111.5	-
EP827 with CNF	AR10-5%	-2.722	-0.8%	-113.3	+1.6%
	AR10-10%	-2.933	+4.0%	-120.5	+8.1%
	AR50-5%	-2.767	+2.2%	-116.2	+4.2%
	AR50-10%	-3.975	+46.1%	-129.8	+16.4%

*Elastic modulus was determined by slope of stress–strain curve between 500 μ strain and 2500 μ strain.

Flexure : Static flexural modulus and strengths of CSNF composites were tested with a screw driven Instron 5500R testing machine. Test method is a three-point bending of 80 mm in span length. A crosshead speed was set to 1.0 mm/min and the crosshead position and loads were measured. A picture of the flexure test is shown in Figure 10. Figure 11 shows stress-displacement curves for EP827 neat resin, AR50-5wt% and AR50-10wt% composites. Table 5 shows the averaged test results of flexural strength and modulus of three data for all types of materials without CF fabric. One remarkable finding is that flexural strength and modulus are improved more than 10% in CSNF composites, except for the strength of AR10-5% composite. AR50-10wt% composite exhibits 42% and 38% higher flexural modulus and strength than neat EP827 resin as control.

Fig. 10 Picture of flexural test

Fig. 11 Stress–displacement curves in flexural for CSNF composites (AR50)

Table 5. Results of flexural test for CSNF composites

Resin	Weight of CNF	Flexural Modulus(GPa)	Effects to modulus* (%)	Max. Flexural Stress(MPa)	Effects to Max. stress(%)
EP827	No CNF dispersion	2.309	–	98.7	–
EP827 with CNF	AR10–5%	2.648	+14.7%	101.5	+2.9%
	AR10–10%	2.707	+17.2%	117.7	+19.3%
	AR50–5%	2.573	+11.4%	110.6	+12.1%
	AR50–10%	3.277	+41.9%	135.8	+37.7%

*Elastic modulus was determined by slope of stress–strain curve between 500 μ strain and 2500 μ strain.

2. Mechanical properties of CFRP using CSNF dispersed resin

Tension: Static tensile strengths and modulus of CFRP using CSNF dispersed resins were tested with an Instron 8502 hydraulic testing machine. The crosshead speed was set to 1.0 mm/min. Strain gages were used for strain measurements. A picture of the tensile test is shown in Figure 12. Figure 13 shows stress-strain curves for CFRP using EP827 neat resin and three-phase composites with AR50-5% and AR50-10% dispersed resin. Table 6 shows the averaged test results of tensile strength and modulus of three data for all types of CFRP material with CSNF. It was found that CFRP tensile strengths and modulus using CSNF dispersed resins are not affected seriously by CSNF. CFRP using AR10 resins are deteriorated in modulus about 7%.

Fig. 12 Picture of Tensile test for CFRP

Fig. 13 Strain–Stress curves in tension for CFRP with CSNF(AR50)

Table 6. Results of tensile test for CFRP using CSNF resin (Vf of fabric=50%)

Resin	Weight of CNF	Tensile Modulus(GPa)	Effects to modulus* (%)	Max. tensile Stress (MPa)	Effects to Max. stress(%)
CF/EP827	No CNF	57.19	–	576.1	–
CF/EP827 with CNF	AR10–5%	53.20	–7.0%	573.2	–0.5%
	AR10–10%	53.25	–6.9%	601.2	4.4%
	AR50–5%	55.26	–3.4%	597.5	3.7%
	AR50–10%	56.24	–1.7%	577.2	0.2%

*Elastic modulus was determined by slope of stress–strain curve between 500 μ strain and 2500 μ strain.

Compression: Static compressive strengths and modulus of CFRP using CSNF dispersed resins were tested in hydraulic testing machine with the inter-grip distance of 14.0 mm as shown in Figure 14. The speed of crosshead was set to 1.0 mm/min. Strain gages were used for strain measurements on both side of specimen. Figure 15 shows stress-strain curve for CFRP using EP827 neat resin, and CFRP using AR50-5% and AR50-10% dispersed resin. Table 7 shows the averaged test results of compressive strength and modulus of three data for all types of composite with CF fabric. It is observed that all CFRP using CSNF dispersed resins are improved in composite modulus and strengths. A remarkable finding is that CFRPs using AR10-10wt% and AR50-5wt% resins show about 15% higher compressive strength than CFRP with neat epoxy as control. Strength improvements of 12% or more were found in composites with fabric and CSNF expect for AR10-5% case.

Fig. 14 Picture of compressive test for CFRP

Fig. 15 Strain–Stress curve in compression for CFRP with CSNF(AR50)

Table 7. Results of compressive test for CFRP using CSNF resin (Vf of fabric=50%)

Resin	Weight of CNF	Compressive Modulus(GPa)	Effects to modulus * (%)	Max. comp. Stress (MPa)	Effects to Max. stress(%)
CF/EP827	No CNF	–50.9	–	–484.7	–
CF/EP827 with CNF	AR10–5%	–58.0	+6.8%	–505.1	+1.30%
	AR10–10%	–55.4	+6.7%	–551.9	+14.3%
	AR50–5%	–52.4	+5.0%	–506.9	+15.0%
	AR50–10%	–51.6	+3.7%	–510.9	+12.1%

*Elastic modulus was determined by slope of stress–strain curve between 500 μ strain and 2500 μ strain.

DISCUSSION

Figure 16 indicates comparison in modulus and strength normalized by EP827 properties for two-phase composites of CSNF and epoxy. The obvious modulus improvements were found in AR10-10wt% tension and AR50-10wt% composite properties. However, most compressive moduli were equivalent or only slightly improved from control data. It is likely understood that increase of dispersed CSNF weight makes higher modulus in composites, although a simple estimation is not enough to describe the relationship between CSNF weight percent and composites properties. In the strength of two-phase CSNF composites, AR50-10wt% is improved obviously in flexural strength. Similarly to the results of CSNF composite modulus, there is a tendency that increase in dispersed CSNF weight makes higher strengths in composites. However, the present data are not enough to describe simple and understandable relationships between CSNF weight percent and composite strengths. Effect of CSNF length on composite properties are neither clear from these data so far.

Figure 17 indicates comparison between CFRP laminates without CSNF as control and CFRP laminates with CSNF dispersed resin in moduli and strengths. In the modulus, it is observed that the tensile moduli of composites with dispersed CSNF are deteriorated and that the behavior is embarrassing found to explain. The compressive modulus is equivalent or slightly higher. In the strength, it is found that the tensile strength is almost equivalent to the CFRP without CSNF and dispersed CSNF matrix can increase compressive strengths of fabric based CFRP using this matrix more than 10% except for AR10-5wt% case, whereas it does not affect very much tensile strengths of CFRP. In summary, although some mechanical properties may be improved in CFRP by dispersed CSNF matrix in general, detailed relationships between weight content of CSNF and those mechanical properties remain ambiguous even after the present experiments. Besides, effect of the CSNF length is not well described through the present data. The following reasons can be counted for explanation of the current ambiguity:

1) Uniform dispersion of CSNF into the epoxy matrix may not be obtained in the dilution process because CSNF-epoxy compounds of 25wt% and 35 wt% are very viscous fluid even at 80°C. It is

(b) Composite Strength

Fig. 16 Normalized CSNF composite properties

(b) CFRP Strength

Fig. 17 Normalized CFRP properties using CSNF dispersed resin

suspected that micro-block of thick CSNF compounds may remain after the mixing process and that homogeneity in the matrix may be deteriorated.

2) Formation of voids is observed in some specimens as shown in Figure 18, sectional image obtained from micro-focus X-ray CT. Although careful selections of low void portions are conducted in the preparation and cutting process of specimens as much as possible, it is inevitable that voids remain in composites after vacuum and cure.

So, it is necessary to improve homogeneous dispersion of CSNF and to decrease void contents in order to stabilize the relationships between CSNF content and mechanical property improvements.

Fig. 18 A Example of voids in CFRP using CSNF dispersed resin

CONCLUSIONS

Static strength tests were carried out to determine mechanical properties of CSNF composites without fabric and CFRP using CSNF dispersed. The following conclusions can be reached.

- 1) Dispersion of CSNF to epoxy may improve in mechanical properties for this two-phase composite. The remarkable result is AR-10wt% dispersed epoxy composites where tension modulus and strength are improved to 45% and 22% compared with neat EP827 properties.
- 2) It can be roughly stated that higher weight content of CSNF makes higher strengths in tension, compression, and flexure in two-phase CSNF composites.
- 3) Impregnation of the CSNF dispersed resin to the CF fabric reinforcements may not affect CFRP laminates modulus and strength in tensile loading.
- 4) Impregnation of the CSNF dispersed resin to the CF fabric reinforcement may improve CFRP laminates modulus and strength in compressive loading.
- 5) Clear monotonic relationships between CSNF weight content and mechanical properties in CF fabric laminates with CSNF matrix cannot be obtained. The effect of CSNF length upon mechanical properties can neither be described.
- 6) It is necessary to improve CSNF dispersion process to achieve homogeneous CSNF matrix and to reduce void formation during composites processing.

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